

Apparent Molal Volume of Potassium Sulphate and Sodium Sulphate Solutions in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 35°

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Redlich and Rosenfeld¹, on the basis of the interionic attraction theory, derived the equation:

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 + a\sqrt{C} + bC$$

where Φ and Φ_0 are the apparent molal volume of the solution at the concentration 'C' and at zero concentration and 'a' and 'b' are two constants. The constant 'a' should be theoretically the same for the same valency type of the solute and 'b' is an empirical one. The above equation reduces to

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 + a\sqrt{C}$$

in dilute solutions. The validity of this theory in aqueous solution has been examined by many workers². Scott, Geffcken, Kruis, Gueker, and others² attribute Φ_0 to an additive character, depending on the constituent ions of the electrolytes in aqueous solution. This has been extended to mixed solvents and the apparent molal volumes of the solutions of potassium sulphate and sodium sulphate in 10, 20, and 30% by weight of dioxane-water mixtures at 35° have been measured. The range of concentration is 0.1M to 0.0025M.

The apparent molal volume (Φ) has been calculated by using the equation:

$$\Phi = \frac{1000}{C} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} - 1 \right) + \frac{M}{\rho_0}$$

where M is the molecular weight of the solute, 'C' is the molar concentration, and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and solvent, respectively. The plot of Φ against $\sqrt{C}$ was found to be linear. The values of Φ_0 and 'a' at different solvent compositions are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent composition (% of dioxane)	K ₂ SO ₄		Na ₂ SO ₄		$\Delta\Phi_0$ (K ₂ SO ₄ —Na ₂ SO ₄)
	Φ_0	a	Φ_0	a	
10	125.00	1.47	74.50	6.45	50.50
20	125.50	1.19	76.00	5.92	49.50
30	..	..	79.50	1.32	..

The density measurements could not be taken at 30% dioxane content in the case of K₂SO₄, as it was not soluble at higher concentrations. It is seen, however, from Table I

1. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **A155**, 55; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 738.

2. Harned and Owen, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 2nd. ed., p. 250.

that Φ_0 increases with the increase of the dioxane content, showing it to be independent on the composition of the solvent. The constant ' α ' is not same for the two electrolytes, though these are of the same valency type. This abnormality was also noticed by Chackravarti and Prasad³.

The difference between the two values of Φ_0 ($\Delta\Phi_0$) is not same at 10% and 20% solvent compositions. So with caution, it can be stated that the additive character of ' Φ_0 ' is not exhibited. Further investigations are in progress.

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